

Democratizing AI: Exploiting Generative AI to Expand Policy Access and Improve Public Participation in Policy-Making in sub-Saharan Africa

Ridwan Sorunke ¹, Malcolm Durosaye ^{2*}, Promise Lawal ³, Godson Oghenechuko ⁴

** Policy Vault, Dev-Afrique Development Advisors
durosayemalcolm@gmail.com*

Abstract

Technologies based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) present an opportunity for Africa to enhance government transparency, drive transformation, and reimagine its economic growth. Its usage could, however, exacerbate existing social and economic inequalities.

This paper focuses on the potential of Generative AI (GenAI) systems based on Large Language Models (LLMs) to expand citizens' access to government policies and promote public participation in policy-making in sub-Saharan Africa. It also explores strategies to mitigate inequality and uphold fundamental rights and freedoms, such as the right to privacy and personal data protection.

This paper has four objectives 1. Assess how GenAI presents opportunities for open governance and citizen participation 2. Analyze national strategies and frameworks for AI by governments in sub-Saharan Africa and their alignment with global standards; 3. Identify obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance 4. Identify challenges and risks posed by AI to governance in Africa and develop recommendations to address data protection and human rights issues. The discussion was informed by strategies and policy documents on AI in Africa and insights from users of GovTech solutions.

Keywords – GenAI; AIforGovernance; AIforPolicyMaking; AIforCitizenParticipation; GovTech

1. Introduction

The use of Generative AI (GenAI) tools like ChatGPT, BingChat, and Google Bard is rapidly expanding. While the public perception of their impact is still developing, studies have confirmed the potential of GenAI to improve access to information globally. Equitable deployment and effective application of Gen AI solutions can be leveraged to expand citizens' access to information, reshape governance, and promote citizen participation in policymaking in Africa. This is particularly important given the challenge of limited access to government policy data and no knowledge of how to participate or contribute to policy making among African citizens.

Several developed countries including the US, Singapore, and the United Kingdom are harnessing the opportunities presented by AI to improve their public services and gain strategic economic advantages (Oxford Insights, 2021; TechCabal 2022). In Africa, a few governments have made efforts toward the development and deployment of AI in their countries. Some of these efforts include adopting regulatory frameworks and partnering with private AI companies. However, the development and deployment of AI continues to experience a slow take-off in Africa, largely due to concerns about the risks associated with AI. A recent example is the suspension of Worldcoin's AI project by the Kenyan authorities over concerns about the security of its citizens (Melody, 2023). To improve AI uptake, it is important for government to explore how AI-based technologies and the disclosure of public data can empower civil society, as well as the disruptive impact of adopting AI for development on African businesses and industries.

1.1 Problem Statement

Policies are very instrumental in the development and progress of nations. They serve as routes for governments to achieve various goals and improve the well-being of their citizens, communities, towns, and countries (Obamwonyi and Aibieyi 2014). Policies are a product of deliberate decision-making processes to address societal needs and promote national development.

However, citizens and organizations, particularly members of civil society in Africa, often struggle to stay updated on newly released government policies and laws due to lack of access. Even when they have access, these policies can be difficult to fully comprehend, limiting their ability to contribute during public consultations and hold their authorities to account. Generative AI based on large language models (LLMs) can process and interpret large policy data for easy comprehension and accessibility. For example, a chatbot system can accept and analyze comprehensive information to provide correct analysis to users. Also, AI can be deployed for quick sorting and analysis of citizens' thoughts and comments on a policy matter during and immediately after public consultations.

For GenAI to be effective in Africa however, there is a need to address certain challenges with AI such as under-representation of African content and lack of transparency in AI models. This is primarily attributable to insufficient training data and private sector dominance of AI model ownership and maintenance. This lack of transparency further exacerbates the problem, as the broader academic community and society cannot easily assess or rectify bias in such closed systems (Madeleine and Vanessa, 2024).

1.2 Research Questions

This research seeks to answer the following questions:

- I. How does GenAI present opportunities for open governance and citizen participation in sub-Saharan Africa?
- II. What are the biggest obstacles and possible solutions to introducing AI in policy-making and governance?
- III. What national strategies and frameworks for AI have been adopted by governments in sub-Saharan Africa and how do they align with global standards?
- IV. What are the challenges and risks posed by AI on governance in Africa and mitigation strategies?

The research findings inform the development of recommendations to address issues around AI model biasness, data protection and human rights.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Data sample

This research engaged a mixed-method approach for data collection and analysis. Data was collected from primary and secondary sources including surveys, focused group discussions, interviews, journals and existing national AI policy documents. Qualitative data collected was analyzed thematically, with quantitative data used to complement qualitative inputs.

2.2 Sampling size and procedure

Given the scope and objectives of the research, a sample size of approximately 84 respondents across regions of sub-Saharan Africa. The respondents were selected to ensure that all relevant stakeholders in the industry are assessed including government stakeholders, researchers, members of civil society, and the private sector. This data was used to complement data collected through surveys and workshops deployed in November 2023 by Policy Vault (PV) on AI and its potential impact on data access.

2.3 Data collection

The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire administered to civil servants, researchers, AI experts, members of civil society, and the private sector through a Microsoft Form. The questionnaire included both closed-ended and open-ended questions, allowing for quantitative analysis of responses as well as qualitative insights into participants' perspectives and experiences.

Secondary data sources include data from UN trade & development Data Protection and Privacy Legislation Worldwide, Oxford Insights Government AI Readiness Index 2023, World Justice Project Rule of Law Index 2023, OECD, National government websites and PolicyVault.

2.4 Methods for data analysis

The methods employed for data analysis in this study:

1. Descriptive statistics consisting of frequency, distribution, and percentages was used to assess **Research Question I**: How does GenAI present opportunities for open governance and citizen participation in sub-Saharan Africa?
2. A Likert-type scale was used to assess **Research Question II and IV**: the obstacles, challenges, and risks posed by AI to African governance. A five-point scale consisting of ordinal measurement (i.e. 1-5) was used to examine the level of seriousness of objective three of this study.
3. Cluster analysis was used to analyze **Research Question III** national strategies and frameworks for AI by governments in sub-Saharan Africa and

their alignment with global standards. The model employed to achieve research objective three was adjusted from the cluster analysis model used by James, Gregory & Kevin (2023) to analyze different countries' national AI strategies (excluding African countries) by categorizing their inclusion of different attributes as either High, Medium, or Low. The attributes were modified for this assessment with a focus on open governance, data protection, AI governance, and readiness for AI adoption.

3. Key Findings

In March 2024, we administered a questionnaire and also did phone interviews with 84 respondents in sub-Saharan Africa to explore opportunities, obstacles, and challenges of AI and LLMs for governance. For this paper, our respondents include government workers, lecturers, researchers, tech experts, and non-governmental organization representatives with roles in IT or experience using GenAI technologies.

- Rwanda stands out as a leader in AI adoption and governance within the sub-Sahara region. It ranks high in the four attributes—open governance, data protection, AI governance, and readiness for AI adoption—as analyzed in the study. South Africa and Mauritius also demonstrate strong performance, appearing in high clusters across three attributes.
- Majority believe that regulatory compliance, anti-corruption promotion, and public service delivery are the areas that will benefit the most from the integration of AI and LLMs.
- Lack of regulatory framework, and ethical concerns are major obstacles to introducing AI in policy-making and governance in Africa.
- Research participants believe limited technical expertise and capacity among government officials may hinder the effective implementation and oversight of AI technologies in governance processes.

4. Recommendations

- Ethical concerns can be addressed by establishing clear and comprehensive regulations for AI development and deployment.
- Deliberate measures and speedy action should be deployed to correct any observed bias.
- Government agencies should adopt AI as a tool to complement traditional methods of servicedelivery for efficiency and cost reduction.

- Government should support capacity-building programs to train government officials, policymakers, and stakeholders on AI technologies and their implications to enhance informed decision-making.

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